

3200, 1600 and 800 cm^{-1} . Low values of pK_a for these drugs ensure that they are almost entirely in the form of the complex forming species (the anion) at the physiological pH 7.3. Formation of only ML and ML_2 complexes indicates that the coordination number six for the metal ion is not attained. This may favour the attachment of the drug-chelate with the tissue, thus binding these drugs with the nucleic acid and affecting the structure and functions of nucleic acids, resulting in beneficial effects.

References

1. E. BOYLAND, O. E. DUKES, P. L. GROVER and C. B. V. MITCHLEY, *Br. J. Cancer*, 1962, **16**, 283.
2. F. J. O. ROE, E. BOYLAND, O. S. DUKES and C. B. V. MITCHLEY, *Br. J. Cancer*, 1965, **19**, 860.
3. G. J. VAN ESOH, H. VAN GENDEREN and H. H. VINK, *Br. J. Cancer*, 1962, **16**, 289.
4. B. ZAWIRSKA and K. MEDRAS, *Zentbl. Allg. Path. Anat.*, 1968, **1**.
5. S. S. EPSTEIN and N. MANTEL, *Experientia*, 1968, **24**, 580.
6. F. W. SUNDERMAN, *Food Cosmet. Toxicol.*, 1971, **9**, 105.
7. A. FRUST, "Chemistry of Chelation in Cancer", Thomas Springfield, 1963.
8. A. TIWARI, H. N. SHARMA and P. B. CHAKRAWARTI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, **19**, 88; A. TIWARI, P. B. CHAKRAWARTI and H. N. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 533; A. TIWARI, H. N. SHARMA and P. B. CHAKRAWARTI, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci., India, Sect. A*, 1981, **51**, 55.
9. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
10. VAN UITERT and C. HASS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **75**, 3651.
11. D. D. FERRIN, "Organic Complexing Agents", Interscience, New York, 1948, p. 51.
12. A. TIWARI, H. N. SHARMA and P. B. CHAKRAWARTI, *Natl. Acad. Sci. Letters*, 1979, **2**, 289.
13. G. HERZBERG, "Molecular Spectra and Molecular Structure, Infra Red and Raman Spectra of Polyatomic Molecules", Van Nostrand, New York, 1947.
14. K. FUJITA, K. NAKAMOTO and M. KOBAYASHI, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 3963.

Chromatographic Behaviour of Copper(II), Cadmium(II), Bismuth(III), Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) Ions in Solvents Containing Dimethyl Sulphoxide

K. RAJAMANI, S. MBENAKSHI and W. T. JANAKI*
PSGR Krishnammal College, Coimbatore-641 004

Manuscript received 21 December 1982, revised 26 March 1984,
accepted 21 July 1984

THE present investigation is aimed at a study of the effect of dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) when admixed with solvents of varying polarity on the

paper chromatographic migrations of cations, namely Cu^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} .

Experimental

Solutions of Cu^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ions were prepared from their salts and the mixed solutions were prepared by mixing their individual solutions in suitable proportions.

Pure isopropanol, n-butanol, methylethylketone, chloroform, ethyl acetate, DMSO, and 50% nitric acid were used as eluents. The binary mixtures consisted of different proportions of DMSO in various solvents and adding a definite percentage of 50% nitric acid to minimise the diffusion and increase the sharpness of the band (Table 1).

Rutter's technique¹ of circular paper chromatography was adopted using 12.5 cm circles of Whatman No. 1 chromatographic paper and the elution carried out until the solvent front reached the premarked boundary. 0.05 to 0.1 ml of the solution was spotted containing 10 to 20 μg of the cations. For the comparison of Rr values of the ions Kawerau's modification of Rutter's technique was adopted. The spots were dried at 50-60° in air oven and the ions detected by spraying yellow ammonium sulphide².

Results and Discussion

In isopropanol, n-butanol, methylethylketone, the cations show only a diffusive migration. Rr values of the ions increases with increase in polarity. In other nonpolar solvents like ester, chloroform the ions do not migrate at all. However, in DMSO all the ions migrated almost to the solvent front. Due to its highly polar and donor nature, DMSO is capable of desorbing the adsorbed ions and subsequently solubilizes the ions due to its complex forming tendency with ions.

As in the case of pure solvents, the rate of migration of the ions increases with an increase in dielectric constant of the binary system. Thus, with higher concentration of DMSO, the Rr value is at its maximum and migration occurs almost to the solvent front, whereas with low proportion of DMSO the migration of ions was restricted. High donor capacity of DMSO is supported by non-linear graphs obtained from plot of Rr values of the ions with dielectric constant.

Quantitative separation of binary and ternary ions is possible with solvent systems such as DMSO : isopropanol : HNO_3 (50%) (20 : 70 : 10); DMSO : n-butanol : HNO_3 (50%) (10 : 84 : 6), (20 : 74 : 6); and DMSO : methylethylketone : HNO_3 (50%) (30 : 60 : 10) (Table 2).

From the above it can be inferred that DMSO plays a dual role in the chromatographic migration of ions on paper in solubilizing the ions, as well as enhancing the rate of migration because of its high polar nature and donor capacity.

TABLE 1—R_r VALUE × 100 OF IONS IN TERNARY SYSTEMS

Solvent system	Cu ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Cd ²⁺	Bi ³⁺
DMSO : n-butanol : HNO ₃ (50%)					
10 : 84 : 6	24	18	24	83	68
20 : 74 : 6	47	46	47	50	68
DMSO : Isopropanol : HNO ₃ (50%)					
10 : 80 : 10	43	31	39	45	69
20 : 70 : 10	65	62	78	65	91
DMSO : Methyl ethyl ketone : HNO ₃ (50%)					
10 : 80 : 10	54	39	43	58	85
20 : 70 : 10	62	63	63	69	94
30 : 60 : 10	79	83	72	86	96
DMSO : Ethyl acetate : HNO ₃ (50%)					
10 : 80 : 10	41	22	23	30	72

TABLE 2—SEPARATION OF BINARY AND TERNARY IONS

Solvent system	Ions separated
DMSO : Isopropanol : HNO ₃ (50%) 20 : 70 : 10	Ni ²⁺ -Bi ³⁺ Co ²⁺ -Cd ²⁺ Bi ³⁺ -Cd ²⁺ Bi ³⁺ -Cu ²⁺ Cd ²⁺ -Bi ³⁺ -Co ²⁺ Cd ²⁺ -Ni ²⁺ -Bi ³⁺ Bi ³⁺ -Cd ²⁺ -Co ²⁺ Ni ²⁺ -Cd ²⁺ -Bi ³⁺
DMSO : n-butanol : HNO ₃ (50%) 10 : 84 : 6 20 : 74 : 6	Co ²⁺ -Bi ³⁺ Co ²⁺ -Cu ²⁺ (d) Ni ²⁺ -Cd ²⁺ Ni ²⁺ Cu ²⁺ (d) Co ²⁺ -Cu ²⁺ -Bi ³⁺ (d) Co ²⁺ -Bi ³⁺ -Cd ²⁺
DMSO : Methyl ethyl ketone : HNO ₃ (50%) 30 : 60 : 10	Ni ²⁺ -Cd ²⁺ -Bi ³⁺ Cu ²⁺ -Bi ³⁺ -Ni ²⁺ Co ²⁺ -Cd ²⁺ -Bi ³⁺

(d)=diffused

References

1. L. RUTTER, *Nature (London)*, 1948, **161**, 435.
2. S. KERTES and M. LEDERER, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1956, **15**, 543.

Further Studies in Multiple Boundary Formation During Electrolysis in a W-tube

SUBHALAKSHMI GHOSH

Department of Physical Chemistry, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta-700 032

Manuscript received 23 April 1983, revised 23 March 1984, accepted 21 July 1984

As early as 1972 Palit^{1,2} made the intriguing observation that on electrolysis of any dilute electrolyte in a W-tube, sharp stationary boundaries form in the inner tubes generally dividing the solution into three zones—acid, neutral and alkaline. The intermediate neutral zone is not only neutral but is practically depleted of all electrolytes, a behaviour which is just opposite to the prediction of the time honoured Hittorf theory and so can be termed an anti-Hittorf phenomenon. Time taken for such boundary formation, multiplicity and sharpness of

the boundaries, if and whenever formed any, depend on the current density, concentration of the electrolyte³, cell geometry, nature of the solvent⁴ and nature of the electrolyte^{4,5}. Sengupta and Palit⁶ also noted the acceleration of boundary formation by exogenous addition of acids, alkalis as well as salts into the original electrolytic solution and put forward a tentative theory to explain this phenomenon. During electrolysis of a potassium dichromate solution under various conditions the present author observed some interesting features in addition to those reported earlier¹⁻⁶ related to the boundary formation phenomenon, and these are enumerated in the present note.

Band formation in outermost limbs: If initially the lower portion of the W-tube be filled with a mixture of potassium dichromate and a concentrated additional electrolyte (e.g. sodium sulphate), the rest with dichromate solution alone, and the system is electrolysed, a colourless band at the anode limb and a deep coloured band at the cathode limb appear. But the development of such a coloured or colourless thin band does not take place, if the entire solution is initially a mixture of potassium dichromate and sodium sulphate.

Double boundary formation in the outermost tube by adding sugar: When the lower part of the W-tube is filled up with a mixture of K₂Cr₂O₇ (0.01 M) and a concentrated sugar solution, and the rest with original dichromate solution (0.01 M), a spectacular boundary formation takes place at the outermost tubes of the W-tube. Initially a colourless band forms in the lower portion of the outermost limb on the cathode side, which gradually spreads out towards the lower portion of the outermost limb on the anode side, current density simultaneously decreasing from 5 to 0.2 mA. The solution above this band assumes light yellow colour on the cathode side and deep brown colour on the anode side. Another important feature of such electrolysis is that no gas formation takes place at all at the intermediate portion of the tube even after prolonged electrolysis.

Effect of adding solid potassium dichromate after double boundary formation with its solution: If about 0.1 g of K₂Cr₂O₇ is added from the cathode